

Treatment of composite chrome tannery wastewater in a Moving Bed Hybrid Bioreactor

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Abstract : The composite chrome tannery wastewater originates from tannery units and contains substantial quantity of slowly-biodegradable substances, which make it incompatible for conventional biological treatment like ASP. Therefore, Moving Bed Hybrid Bioreactor (MBHBR) can be selected for treating this type of wastewater, as it is capable to handle the wastewater containing slowly biodegradable substance. Looking into this matter, the present research study was undertaken to find out the performance of MBHBR system for treatment of composite chrome tannery wastewater. The MBHBR system was run under continuous mode of operation at different bio-carrier variations i.e. 50 g/L, 75 g/L and 100 g/L under 3(three) different HRT combinations viz. 8, 10 and 12 h. In this study, maximum 85% COD removal efficiency was observed for a bio-carrier concentration of 100 g/L, hydraulic retention time of 8 h and organic loading rate (OLR) of 7.5 kg/m³/day under an initial COD concentration of 2500 mg/L.

Keywords : Moving Bed Hybrid Bioreactor (MBHBR), performance study, composite wastewater, chrome tannery COD removal.

I. Introduction

Treatment of Chrome tannery wastewater becomes difficult due to various toxic/inhibitory substances present in the effluent. There are many research studies on chrome tannery wastewater treatment pertaining to physical, chemical and biological methods. In general, biological treatment process is found ineffective for direct application because of adverse effects by toxic chromium, sulphide, chloride etc. Moreover, biological methods were employed mainly for a few sub-processes generating significant amount of organic matter and having no chromium, chloride etc. Although there is a number of biological methods which are used for the treatment of composite chrome tannery wastewater, like ASP, SBR, UASB etc., their performance is not up to satisfactory level. As a result, treatment of chrome tannery wastewater in a conventional biological system found practically ineffective. In the past two decades many research studies were carried out in the field of up-gradation

of existing wastewater treatment plant with a view to remove both carbonaceous and nitrogenous matter in presence of toxic environment. Apart from that enhanced removal of nutrients along with carbonaceous matter in a single reactor also required a great attention¹. Now a days it has been growing interest among the Engineers and Scientist to develop a cost effective as well as space effective treatment technology without compromising the performance and also to increase the treatment efficiency. One innovative outcome of this research is Moving Hybrid Bioreactor which can be a good and viable treatment option for chrome tannery wastewater.

Very few research studies have been reported in case of treatment of tannery wastewater using Hybrid bio-reactor system. A shaft-type hybrid bioreactor has been developed and studied for treatment of segregated chrome tannery wastewater². In order to compare the performance of Hybrid system with conventional biological system the said reactor was run

firstly under suspended growth and thereafter under Hybrid system having 5 mm sized tyre tube beads as an attachment surface with an amount of 10–30 g/L. Results revealed that Hybrid system performs better than conventional system at higher organic loading rate. Maximum 70.9% COD removal was observed under the higher organic loading rate of 5.250 kg/day/m³. Moreover sludge settleability was also better in case of Hybrid system due to addition of bio-carriers. Similarly a performance study of tannery wastewater in a hybrid up-flow anaerobic sludge blanket (HUASB) was examined over a period of 370 d, at two hydraulic retention times (HRT) viz. 60 and 70 h and two different organic loading rates (OLR) of 2.74 kg COD m⁻³ d⁻¹ and 3.14 kg COD m⁻³ d⁻¹, respectively³. The combined system showed very stable performance in terms of COD removal under the higher organic loading rate with an average removal efficiency 65–91% at a HRT of 70 h and 63–89% at a HRT of 60 h respectively.

Although a very few literatures are available on MBHBR system treating Chrome Tannery wastewater, it seems to be a good and viable treatment option for chrome tannery wastewater. Looking into this matter, research study was carried out in a laboratory scale Moving Bed Hybrid Bioreactor for treatment of composite chrome tannery wastewater in order to evaluate its performance in terms of COD removal.

II. Materials and methods

A. Collection and characterization of composite chrome tannery wastewater

In the present study, raw composite tannery wastewater was collected from a chrome tannery cluster near Kolkata, West Bengal, India. The chrome tanning units, present in this cluster process raw cow/buffalo hides to wet blue leather. In order to characterize the composite chrome tannery wastewater the sample was brought to the Environmental Engineering Laboratory of Civil Engineering Department, IEST, Shibpur. Characterization of the wastewater samples was performed on the basis of following parameters viz. pH, Total solids (TS), Total suspended solids (TSS), Dissolved oxygen (DO), Bio-

chemical oxygen demand (BOD₃ at 27°C), Chemical oxygen demand (COD), Total kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), Ammonium nitrogen (NH₄⁺-N), Nitrate nitrogen (NO₃⁻-N), Total phosphorous (PO₄³⁻), Chloride (Cl⁻), Total alkalinity, Sulphate (SO₄²⁻), Total chromium (Cr³⁺ and Cr⁶⁺) etc. as per Standard Methods⁴. The details of characterization results are furnished in Table 1.

Table 1. Characterization of composite chrome tannery wastewater

Parameter	Measured value
pH	8.64
Total solid (mg/L)	11414
Total suspended solid (mg/L)	1225
Total dissolved (mg/L)	9723
Chlorides (mg/L)	3614
Sulphate (mg/L)	1961
COD (mg/L)	10880
(BOD) ₅ at 20°C (mg/L)	3780
Ammoniacal nitrogen (mg/L as N)	129
Total kjeldahl nitrogen (mg/L as N)	292
Total phosphorus (mg/L)	10
Total chromium as Cr ³⁺ (mg/L)	102
Chromium as Cr ⁶⁺ (mg/L)	5.7

B. Experimental setup

A 15 L capacity PVC bucket was considered as the main aeration tank for laboratory scale Moving Bed Hybrid Bioreactor. A small cube shaped hallow media (dimension 1 cm × 1 cm × 1 cm) was employed as bio-carrier to provide attachment surface for growing up the bio-film. A common 10 mm diameter flexible pipe was built at the center of the aeration tank and connected through the junction box by which the aeration was provided into the reactor. Compressed air was distributed through eight (8) numbers of vertical pipes. One inlet CPVC 10 mm diameter pipe and one outlet CPVC of the same diameter were connected in the reactor at opposite to each other. Outlet pipe coming out from the reactor was extended to the secondary clarifier (PVC made, 5.5 liter capacity) which was placed in a PVC tub for collecting the overflow from the secondary clarifier. There was no biomass recirculation system from sec-

ondary clarifier to main reactor. A sludge withdrawal port was also provided at the bottom of the reactor. The schematic diagram of Moving Bed Hybrid Bioreactor and moving bed bio-carrier are shown in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b.

Fig. 1a. Schematic diagram of Moving Bed Hybrid Bioreactor.

Fig. 1b. Schematic diagram of Moving Bed Bio-carrier.

C. Analytical method

During the entire study, samples were taken from overflow of the secondary clarifier at different time intervals, filtered through commercial grade filter paper, and analyzed for the relevant parameters like pH, COD, MLSS, $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$, Cr^{3+} and Cr^{6+} . The parameters were measured as per Stan-

dard Methods⁴. Cr^{6+} concentration was measured in a few effluent samples selectively, which always showed almost zero value. Attached biomass density was measured by washing the biofilm surface with 25 ml 0.1 (N) NaOH and subsequently by determining protein concentration in the washout as per Lowry's method⁵.

D. Experimental studies

A continuous study was performed using chrome tannery wastewater as influent with varying HRTs viz. 8, 10 and 12 h and varying suspended as well as attached biomass concentrations (50–100 g/L). The reactor was run under influent COD ranging between (1000–2500) mg/L to evaluate the performance of MBHBR. Each continuous run under a particular operating condition was monitored until the quasi-steady state condition reached in the reactor system. There were 12 (twelve) numbers of continuous run, each of 36 h, performed on the MBHBR system with 3 (three) HRT variations i.e. 8, 10 and 12 h and three (3) variations of input bio-carrier concentrations i.e. 50, 75 and 100 g/L. The reactor was fed with the desired flow rate of wastewater using peristaltic pump until quasi-steady state condition reached. The compressed air was injected in the reactor using a blower type air pump. The effluent sample was taken from the overflow of the secondary clarifier for measuring final COD concentration, whereas the reactor content was taken for determining steady state suspended biomass concentration.

III. Results and discussion

A. Details of continuous study

The MBHBR system was run using diluted composite chrome tannery wastewater with an average COD concentration (1000–2500) mg/L, under continuous mode of operation. During the continuous study, HRT was provided in the range of (8–12) h, whereas, the MLSS concentration was maintained between (2000–3000) mg/L. The bio-carrier concentration was varied in the range of (50–100) g/L with an average attached biomass concentration (2000–4000) mg/L respectively. Diluted wastewater samples were prepared by adding plain water with different

Table 2. Results of performance study under continuous mode with composite chrome wastewater in Laboratory scale MBHBR

Run No.	COD concentration		Total biomass concentration (mg/L)	F/M ratio (d ⁻¹)	Organic loading rate (kg/m ³ /day)	COD Removal efficiency (%)
	Influent (mg/L)	Effluent (mg/L)				
1	1000	205	4000	0.75	3	80
2	1000	172	4000	0.6	2.5	83
3	1000	130	4000	0.5	2	87.0
4	1500	220	5250	0.857	4.5	85.0
5	1500	195	5250	0.685	3.6	87
6	1500	182	5250	0.571	3	88
7	2000	295	6500	0.923	6	82
8	2000	245	6500	0.738	4.8	84
9	2000	230	6500	0.615	4	85
10	2500	355	7000	1.071	7.5	85
11	2500	315	7000	0.857	6	87
12	2500	265	7000	0.714	5	88

dilution ratio in the range of 1 : 5 to 1 : 3. Nutrients (Nitrogen and Phosphorus) were fed into the system accordingly in order to maintain a COD : N : P ratio of 20 : 5 : 1. Twelve (12) sets of continuous study was carried out with varying influent COD, HRT and bio-carrier concentration. The results of performance study under continuous mode of operation in MBHBR system are presented in Table 2.

The COD concentration profiles for various continuous runs in MBHBR system using composite chrome wastewater are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively. It has been observed from Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 that the effluent COD concentration rapidly decreased with the progress of time at the initial stage and then reached to a steady value. The COD concentration profiles for each influent COD concentration level, viz. 1000 mg/L are closed together indicating no tangible variation in respect of HRT (Fig. 2). However, the COD concentration profiles for influent COD 1500 mg/L are considerably different from those for influent COD 1000 mg/L, depicting the positive effect of attached biomass in case of the bio-carrier concentration 75 g/L. Apart from that the steady state COD values are observed to be almost same corresponding different HRTs. When the influent COD concentration increased to 2000

mg/L onward, marginal difference in COD profiles was also observed (Fig. 3). As a result, their steady state COD values also appeared to be very much closed to each other, implying no detrimental effect due to increase in COD.

Fig. 2. Effluent COD concentration profile for MBHBR system under continuous mode of operation with composite chrome tannery wastewater [COD concentration : (1000–1500) mg/L].

The COD removal efficiency for different continuous runs using composite chrome tannery wastewater is plotted with respect to volumetric COD load-

Fig. 3. Effluent COD concentration profile for MBHBR system under continuous mode of operation with composite chrome tannery wastewater [COD concentration : (2000–2500) mg/L].

ing rate as shown in Fig. 4. It has been observed from Fig. 4 that COD removal efficiency decreased almost linearly with the increase in volumetric COD loading rate. The profiles of COD removal efficiency are observed to be almost parallel with each other, implying more or less uniform rate of decrease in all the influent COD concentrations. The volumetric COD loading rate varied between (2–7.5) kg COD/day/m³, resulting in variation of COD removal efficiency between (87–85)%. The rate of decrease in

Fig. 4. Plot of COD removal efficiency vs volumetric loading rate for MBHBR system under continuous operation with composite chrome tannery wastewater.

COD removal efficiency with respect to volumetric COD loading rate appears to be low in each set of continuous runs.

The COD removal efficiency for different continuous runs using composite chrome tannery wastewater is plotted with respect to (F/M) ratio (COD basis) as shown in Fig. 5. It has been observed from Fig. 5 that COD removal efficiency decreases linearly with the increase in (F/M) ratio (COD basis). The profiles of COD removal efficiency are observed to have decreasing slope, implying slower rate of decrease for higher influent COD concentrations. The (F/M) ratio (COD basis) varied between (0.5–1.0) d⁻¹, resulting in variation of COD removal efficiency between (87–85)%. The rate of decrease in COD removal efficiency with respect to (F/M) ratio (COD basis) appears to be extremely low in case of highest influent COD concentration, i.e. 2500 mg/L.

Fig. 5. Plot of COD removal efficiency vs (F/M) ratio (COD basis) for MBHBR system under continuous operation with composite chrome tannery wastewater.

B. Discussion of continuous study

The composite chrome tannery wastewater contained a mean COD and BOD₅ of 10800 and 3780 mg/L respectively, exhibiting a slowly bio-degradable character. The significant amounts of non-bio-degradable inorganic substances present in the chrome tannery wastewater make it slowly biodegradable and also incompatible for conventional biological treatment like ASP. Therefore, moving bed hybrid bioreactor (MBHBR) was opted for treating this

wastewater, as it is already established that MBHBR is capable to treat organic wastewater in presence of toxic/inhibitory substance. However, the huge amount of BOD₅/COD present in composite chrome tannery wastewater is not directly treatable by any aerobic biological system. In view of that dilution of the raw wastewater becomes extremely necessary to bring down the BOD₅/COD within tolerable range, i.e. 2500 mg/L of BOD₅ for the aerobic system. Hence, the present raw chrome tannery wastewater was diluted for the continuous study in such a way that a variable COD concentration can be set in the range of (1000–2500) mg/L of COD, with an incremental COD of 500 mg/L.

The suspended biomass (MLSS) and the attached biomass concentration were varied in the range of (2000–3000) mg/L and (2000–4000) mg/L respectively for the influent COD concentration between (1000–2500) mg/L. The attached biomass was provided with a comparatively higher amount to check inhibitory effect caused by the non-biodegradable constituents. The attached biomass, expressed in terms of equivalent suspended biomass revealed that about 1000 mg/L of the attached biomass can be supported by each 25 g/L of the bio-carrier. Therefore, 2000, 3000 and 4000 mg/L of the attached biomass (equivalent suspended biomass) was obtained by providing 50, 75 and 100 g/L of the bio-carriers. Suspended biomass concentration was maintained to a maximum value of 3000 mg/L, because it is the limiting MLSS to ensure good settleability in the secondary clarifier of ASP system. Hence, the total biomass in the MBHBR system was maintained in the range of (4000–7000) mg/L, which would not have been possible to maintain in the ASP, even under extended aeration system.

Hydraulic retention time (HRT) in the MBHBR was provided as (8–12) h. As a result the volumetric loading rate was varied in the range of (2–3), (3–4.5), (4–6) and (5–7.5) kg COD/m³/day for the influent COD concentration of 1000, 1500, 2000 and 2500 mg/L respectively. Similarly, (F/M) ratio (COD basis) varied ranging between (0.5–0.75), (0.57–0.86), (0.61–0.92) and (0.71–1.07) day⁻¹ for the in-

fluent COD concentration of 1000, 1500, 2000 and 2500 mg/L respectively. The continuous study was run without any recirculation of biomass settled in the secondary clarifier, which was possible only due to presence of attached biomass on the bio-carriers. The COD removal efficiency varied in the range of about (80–87)% for the volumetric loading rate between (3–2) kg COD/m³/day and (F/M) ratio between (0.75–0.50) day⁻¹ under the influent COD concentration of 1000 mg/L. Similarly, a volumetric loading rate in the range of (4.5–3.0) kg COD/m³/day and (F/M) ratio between (0.86–0.57) day⁻¹ resulted in a COD removal efficiency varying between (85–88)% under an influent COD concentration 1500 mg/L.

On the other hand, the COD removal efficiency ranged between (82–85)% for the volumetric loading rate in the range of (6–4) kg COD/m³/day and (F/M) ratio between (0.92–0.61) day⁻¹ for the influent COD concentration of 2000 mg/L. Lastly, a volumetric loading rate ranging between (7.5–5.0) kg COD/m³/day and (F/M) ratio between (1.07–0.71) day⁻¹ ensure a COD removal efficiency varying between (85–88)% under an influent COD concentration 2500 mg/L. The results clearly revealed that even under an influent COD concentration 2500 mg/L and a total biomass concentration of about 7000 mg/L, maximum 88% COD removal could occur in the MBHBR system. This finding is tallying with that reported in another study dealing with treatment of chrome tannery wastewater in a hybrid bioreactor². In that continuous study with segregated chrome tannery wastewater, 67.4% COD removal occurred under an influent COD concentration 2500 mg/L and in presence of total biomass concentration about 4320 mg/L.

IV. Conclusion

It can be concluded from the present research study that the Moving Bed Hybrid Bioreactor (MBHBR) system performs better than conventional biological system in case of composite chrome tannery wastewater. However, the biodegradation of composite chrome tannery wastewater inherently exhibited slow rate due to toxicity and substantial

amount of slowly biodegradable substances present in wastewater. However, the MBHBR system is still capable to treat this type of wastewater containing slowly biodegradable substance. The main reason is that in MBHBR system suspended biomass removes easily biodegradable substances and slowly biodegradable substance can be removed by attached biomass. Maximum 85% COD removal efficiency was achieved at an organic loading rate 7.5 kg COD/m³/day, under HRT 8 h and bio-carrier concentration 100 g/L in the MBHBR system. It implies that MBHBR is capable to withstand higher organic loading rate than the conventional ASP for any desired removal efficiency. A low (F/M) ratio (COD basis) can also be maintained in MBHBR by addition of microorganisms attached on the bio-carriers which

enhance the removal efficiency. It was further concluded that the rate of organics removal can be increased by adding more and more bio-carrier concentration.

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